

Comparing Stump Closure Techniques: Polymeric Clips vs. Extracorporeal Knots in Laparoscopic Appendectomy

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Abstract:

Background: Appendicitis is the second most common abdominal pathology necessitating emergency surgery, with a 7-10% lifetime risk in the general population. The primary cause of appendicitis is lumen obstruction, predominantly due to fecoliths. Other causes of lumen obstruction include lymphoid hyperplasia, intestinal worms, and tumors, which can also lead to acute appendicitis. Laparoscopic Appendectomy has become the gold standard for appendectomy, even in cases of complicated appendicitis. With the increased adoption of Laparoscopic Appendectomy, there have been variations in procedural techniques such as port placement, types of anesthesia, criteria for converting to open surgery, and methods for ligating the appendix stump.

Ligating the base of the appendix is a critical step in Appendectomy. In Laparoscopic Appendectomy, where tactile feedback is limited, the choice of method for stump closure becomes particularly important for ensuring safety. Polymeric clips have emerged as a new technique for stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy due to their ease of application, adaptability, rapid application time, and cost-effectiveness.

Methods: The research involved 50 patients who underwent laparoscopic appendectomy from September 2023 to August 2024. Data on patients' demographics, surgical duration, hospital stay length, and complications were retrospectively gathered from medical records. Based on the method used for stump closure, patients were categorized into two groups: one with polymeric endoclip closure and the other with extracorporeal knot.

Results: Our results demonstrate that using a polymeric clip to close the base of the appendix during Laparoscopic Appendectomy is a feasible and safe technique, proving effective for patients with appendicitis. This method offers a practical alternative to the conventional approach of using an extracorporeal knot for stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy.

Conclusion: Our study aimed to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of polymeric clips versus extracorporeal knots for closing the stump during Laparoscopic Appendectomy.

Keywords: Appendectomy, Laparoscopic Appendectomy, Extracorporeal knot, Polymeric Clip.

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Introduction

Appendicitis is one of the most common abdominal pathology which requires emergency surgical intervention with 8-10% lifetime risk in general population [1]. Antibiotic treatment is applied in few cases but surgery remains main choice of treatment. Leading cause for appendicitis and lumen obstruction is lumen obstruction which is caused by fecolith. Other caused are Lymphoid hyperplasia, tumors, intestinal worms etc [2,3]. Fitz described appendicitis in 1886, there have been many studies about appendicitis and the fact that a prompt intervention is required to prevent many serious consequences such as perforation [3]. The

management of appendicitis have gone through revolutionary changes ranging from antibiotics and conservative approach to the surgical treatment of appendicitis which includes Open Appendectomy, Laparoscopic Appendectomy, Natural orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery (minimally invasive). Gold standard for appendectomy is Laparoscopic Appendectomy, including complicated appendicitis. Surgical treatment is main stay of treatment. Open appendectomy is comparatively safe and easy method of surgery. Laproscopic appendectomy is superior because of its advantages, namely, less post-operative pain,

rapid recovery, less hospital stay, cosmetically superior and better vision of lower abdominal quadrants.

Even though surgical technique of Laparoscopic Appendectomy is thoroughly researched, there remain concerns about methods for closing the stump of appendix. Controversies exist regarding this key point in the procedure of stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy as dangerous complications such as entero-cutaneous fistula, peritonitis and sepsis.

As Laparoscopic Appendectomy is becoming more common, the variations in technicalities of the procedure regarding port placement, mode of anaesthesia, methods used for ligation of the stump of appendix⁴. Ligating the base of appendix is a very important step during Appendectomy and it is very crucial to choose the safest method. Division of the appendix and mesoappendix is a critical step in laparoscopic appendectomy and illustrates such variations [5]. Various mechanical devices such as linear endoscopic staplers⁶, metal or non-metal (titanium or polymeric) endoclips [7], harmonic scalpel [7], or ligature devices including preformed endoloops [7], intracorporeal laparoscopic suturing [7], and extracorporeal knots are employed for stump closure in laparoscopic appendectomy. However, the gold standard or optimal method remains uncertain. The use of endoscopic staplers is quicker and potentially safer than endoloops, despite being more costly. Polymeric clips have recently emerged as a promising technique for

stump closure in laparoscopic appendectomy due to their ease of use, adaptability, rapid application, and cost-effectiveness [8,9].

Methodology

Materials and Methods: Diagnosed cases of patients with appendicitis from the Surgery OPD admitted in Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur.

Study Design: Patients written and informed consent was taken from them in their own vernacular language.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients willing to take part in the study and provide written and informed consent
2. Clinically and radiologically diagnosed cases of acute appendicitis, subacute appendicitis, chronic appendicitis.
3. Patients of all age groups

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Immunocompromised state and pregnant patients
2. Patients with severe pulmonary disease
3. Generalized peritonitis
4. Perforation at the base of appendix in perforated appendicitis or appendicular mass.

Patients were then divided into two groups by block randomization method using lottery method and was assigned one of the groups, Group A and group B.

Figure 1: GROUP A: Stump closure using polymeric clip will be done in this group.

Figure 2: GROUP B: Stump closure using extracorporeal knot will be done in this group.

Sample Size: 50 (25 in each group.)

Study Duration: For a period of 1 year

Study Centre: The study was done in the department of general surgery at Mahatma Gandhi medical college and hospital, Jaipur.

Table 1: Mean Operative time (in Minutes)

Groups	Mean time (minutes)
Group A	50 mins
Group B	60 mins

Table 2: Mean time for applying polymeric clip and extracorporeal knot (in minutes) in Groups

Groups	Mean time (minutes)
Group A	4 mins
Group B	8 mins

Table 3: Complications

Groups	Stump leak	Infections
Group A	2	1
Group B	3	2

Post-operative recovery: Relatively same in both groups

Result

Our findings indicate that utilizing a polymeric clip for closing the base of the appendix during Laparoscopic Appendectomy is both feasible and safe, proving to be an effective procedure for patients with appendicitis. This approach serves as a viable alternative to the traditional method of using an extracorporeal knot for stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy. Although several retrospective studies have supported the feasibility and advantages of stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy, our study specifically highlights the advantages of the polymeric clip. The

polymeric clip method offers the benefits of speed and safety but comes at a higher cost compared to using endoloops for stump closure, which is a more economical alternative albeit requiring specific Laparoscopic skills. Concerns have been raised regarding the potential for spilled clips to increase the incidence of peritoneal adhesions, potentially leading to intestinal obstruction due to adhesions. However, a recent randomized clinical trial has demonstrated that the use of polymeric endoclips is reliable and reduces intraoperative time when employed for stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy [10]. Polymeric clips find extensive application in various minimally invasive procedures. They have been established as safe and effective for ligating structures such as the cystic

duct, ureter, and vessels up to 16mm in diameter ever since their introduction. The clip applicator, designed for use through a 10-mm port, is straightforward, requiring no learning curve and facilitating easy replication.

Our study specifically examined the use of polymeric clips for stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy. We observed no increase in intraoperative or postoperative complications associated with their use, no instances of clip slippage, and no occurrences of obstruction due to adhesions related to the clip.

In our assessment, we recommend considering the use of polymeric clips for closing the appendicular stump in Laparoscopic Appendectomy when the base of the appendix measures 10mm or less in diameter, and there is no perforation at the base that would preclude its safe application.

However, in cases of severe inflammation or perforation at the base, or when the size of the base does not permit safe use of polymeric clips, alternative methods such as extracorporeal knots or endostaplers may be more suitable for the procedure. Ultimately, the overall condition and size of the base of the appendix are crucial factors in determining whether to use a polymeric clip or an extracorporeal knot for stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy.

Conclusion

In summary, our study aimed to compare the efficacy of polymeric clips versus extracorporeal knots for stump closure in Laparoscopic Appendectomy. We enrolled a total of 50 patients diagnosed with appendicitis, randomly assigning 25 patients each to groups A and B using a block randomization table. The primary criterion influencing the decision to use a polymeric clip for appendicular stump closure was the overall condition and size of the appendix base. Our study revealed that using polymeric clips did not result in increased intraoperative or postoperative complications compared to using extracorporeal knots. Secondary outcomes such as the timing of oral feeds initiation, discharge day, and postoperative pain were not significantly affected by the method of appendicular stump closure.

Additionally, the polymeric clip group demonstrated shorter mean operative times and quicker closure times compared to the extracorporeal knot group. The tactile feedback provided by polymeric clip application served as an additional checkpoint to ensure effective stump

closure, which is not available with extracorporeal knots where operators rely mainly on visual cues. Due to its shorter learning curve, ease of application, reproducibility, cost-effectiveness, comparable complication rates, and reduced operator variability, the polymeric clip method has the potential to emerge as a preferred choice for appendicular stump closure in appropriate surgical settings.

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